

SKILLBILL

Working Group Insights

skillbill

SKILL TO BOOST INNOVATION & PROFESSIONAL
FULFILLMENT IN A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY

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1. Introduction

This document summarises the key highlights from the SKILLBILL four working groups

1.1 SKILLBILL at a glance

SKILLBILL aimed at creating several paths towards **increased skills** with **innovative learning methods**, having as its ultimate goal the **renewable energy acceleration**. To achieve this, the project was set to greatly enhance **cooperation** between key players (stakeholders), using **open discussion** through a Stakeholder Joint Initiative, gaining access to useful insights into **training needs and practices**.

1.2 The four Working Groups

In SKILLBILL, **four thematic Working Groups** were established, each concentrating on a critical area of renewable energy and fuel technologies. Each thematic Working Group was designed to bring together experts from different disciplines and collaboratively **address challenges and develop solutions**. The thematic focus areas are:

Renewable Electricity: Focusing on the development, integration, and optimisation of renewable electricity sources such as solar, wind, and hydroelectric power. It addresses issues related to grid stability, storage solutions, and smart grid technologies.

Biofuels and Renewable Fuels: Concentrating on the production, sustainability, and scalability of biofuels and other renewable fuels, this group explores advanced biofuel technologies, feedstock availability, and lifecycle assessments.

Renewable Heat: Targeting the generation and utilisation of renewable heat sources, including geothermal, solar thermal, and biomass heating systems. It examines energy efficiency, district heating, and innovative heating technologies.

Sustainable Mobility: Aiming to develop and promote sustainable transportation solutions, this group focuses on electric vehicles, hydrogen fuel cells, and sustainable urban mobility strategies. It investigates infrastructure needs, policy frameworks, and market adoption barriers.

The Working Groups met every six months in order to discuss several topics as presented in the figure on the right:

Figure 1. Working Group Meetings

2. Summary and Comparative Analysis of Actionable Results

2.1.1 Summary per Working Groups' recommendations

Table 1. Summary of Working Groups' Recommendations

Electricity	Mobility	Fuels	Heat
<p>Policy & Market Enablers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design targeted incentives such as subsidies and tax breaks for innovative renewable projects to accelerate R&D. • Reward energy communities for active participation, awareness-raising, and equipment maintenance. • Engage local stakeholders with renewable installers, especially in energy-poor areas, to build trust and support. • Support policy for inclusive upskilling and gender balance, with incentives for committed companies. • Promote the European Renewable Academy to serve as a centre of excellence in renewables, hydrogen, and batteries. 	<p>Policy, Planning & Infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentivise sustainable mobility: Tax breaks, subsidies, and usage incentives for electric vehicles (EVs) and related infrastructure. • Adopt and integrate EU laws: Embed EU regulations like AFIR into national policies to streamline implementation (e.g. charger installation, public space allocation). • Develop national frameworks: Address legal gaps in countries like Greece for multi-use public space (pedestrians, EV chargers, cyclists, lockers). • Support sustainable urban & rural planning: Promote mixed-use zones, remote work, and efficient public transport systems, particularly in non-urban areas. • Design accurate charging infrastructure networks: Plan comprehensive EV charging strategies at the national and EU levels. 	<p>Policy & Market Activation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce taxes for renewable fuels to minimise the cost gap with fossil alternatives and stimulate market adoption. • Simplify legislation and permitting for renewable fuel production to speed up deployment. • Address market heterogeneity by harmonising EU-wide regulations for renewable fuels. • Incentivise alternative vehicle types (e.g. hybrids, methane cars) to diversify clean transport options beyond EVs. • Support combustion engine compatibility with synthetic fuels for sectors difficult to electrify (e.g. heavy-duty transport). 	<p>Strategic Priorities & Systemic Integration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentivise waste heat recovery into District Heating Networks (DHNs) and Renewable Heat Communities (RHCs), especially from industrial sources. • Promote standardisation of heat-related values (e.g. waste heat, heat loss) is a critical first step toward effective energy planning. • Promote local sector integration (heating, cooling, electricity, waste heat) with an emphasis on synergies and local energy sources. • Support recognition of Renewable Heating Communities in national and EU frameworks to increase visibility and support.
<p>Regulatory & Funding Innovation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support flexible funding models with multiple promising projects per call, using unallocated funds. • Balance between high TRL and basic research: Innovation funding must deliver results without undermining fundamental R&D. • Design stronger project benchmarking mechanisms to retain and reconsider strong unfunded proposals. 	<p>Behavioural & Cultural Change</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilise favour nudging over mandates by using behavioural economics to encourage sustainable transport habits rather than imposing strict regulations. • Raise public awareness addressing cultural resistance to EVs and other sustainable options, particularly in fossil fuel-dependent regions. 	<p>Infrastructure & Supply Chain Readiness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support sustainable supply chains for inputs like biomethane, including the use of catch crops and food/agricultural by-products. • Broaden R&D focus beyond EVs to include synthetic fuels, Power-to-X, and biomethane to future-proof the energy transition. 	<p>Financing & Policy Levers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage credit institutions as public authorities should negotiate for low-interest loans, linking grant eligibility to credit conditions. • Increase EU funding to support pilot projects, data-driven planning, and academia-industry collaboration. • Support more case studies and pilots to show the value of waste heat recovery and District Heat Networks to industries and local governments.

Electricity	Mobility	Fuels	Heat
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support public financing for individuals adopting clean mobility technologies, especially hybrids and gas vehicles. 	
<p>Skills & Education Priorities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support Train-the-Trainers programs to ensure knowledge transfer and broad workforce readiness. • Integrate cross-disciplinary curricula, incl. PV, batteries, smart cities, etc., through project-based learning. • Highlight the need for Big Data, AI & analytics as professionals in smart grids and predictive systems are critical for grid integration. • Strengthen interdisciplinary research centres to link academia, IT, and engineering for end-to-end energy solutions. 	<p>Innovation & Engagement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduce AI in mobility by developing seminars on applying artificial intelligence for efficiency and automation in mobility systems. • Use AR/VR for young learners: Foster early interest in sustainable mobility careers through immersive technology. • Strengthen stakeholder collaboration, engaging academia, industry, and policymakers to co-develop relevant, future-proof curricula. 	<p>Awareness & Public Engagement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organise public campaigns and site visits to raise awareness and build trust around renewable fuels. • Promote realistic narratives beyond EVs, emphasising the role of biofuels, methane, and synthetic options in the green transition. • Highlight the climate neutrality and versatility of new fuels to counter resistance and stimulate public interest. 	<p>Skills & Workforce Development</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote incentives for skilled workers and industrial PhDs to meet the growing demand for heat-sector expertise. • Design hands-on VET training & industry traineeships across degree levels to align education with real-world heating sector needs. • Boost digital skills for performance monitoring in heating systems and smart infrastructure management. • Integrate statistics and data analysis into energy-related study programs to support evidence-based decision-making.
<p>Community & Workforce Engagement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support and incentivise grassroots energy communities to drive local adoption and skill-building. • Strengthen industry-academia collaboration to ensure education aligns with future workforce needs. • Foster niche expertise to improve competitiveness and innovation in the green energy labour market. 	<p>Education, Training & Workforce Skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Align training with industry needs: Ensure education programs reflect current and future demands in sustainable mobility and e-mobility. • Train engineers in soft skills such as engagement and behaviour change to support mobility transitions. • Upskill in EV maintenance: Offer hands-on workshops in electric vehicle diagnostics, repair, and service. • Integrate advanced simulation software for training in smart transport systems 	<p>Education & Training Priorities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include EU fuel policies (e.g. Renewable Energy Directive) in energy-related education curricula. • Train public authorities on fuel technologies, applications, and product properties. • Upgrade VET programs to include new fuel tech, maintenance, and safety. • Integrate green finance and business into engineering education to align skills with emerging market needs. • Offer training on by-product utilisation to enhance feedstock knowledge across the agriculture and food sectors. 	<p>Innovation & Collaboration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create cross-disciplinary working groups to tackle complex heating transition challenges. • Organise hackathons linking students and industries for real-world problem solving. • Enhance understanding of energy/environmental policy compliance through targeted training in legal and regulatory interpretation.

2.1.2 Categorisation of Recommendations

The table below offers an aggregated and categorised version of the actionable outcomes of the WG meetings.

Table 2. Aggregated and categorised results from the WGs

Category	Recommendation	Brief Description
Political/Regulatory	Subsidies/tax breaks for innovative renewable energy projects	Provide subsidies and tax breaks by governments to foster innovation in renewable energy, encouraging investment in R&D.
	National laws in favour of renewable energy projects	Promote the responsible use of energy from renewable sources through incentives and the integration of European regulations into national policies.
	Tax fossil energy derivatives	Implement taxes on fossil energy derivatives to make renewable alternatives more competitive and encourage a shift towards sustainable energy.
	Simplification of legislation and permission processes	Simplify the legislative and permission processes for renewable energy projects to encourage faster adoption and implementation.
	Integrate nudging-style measures instead of compulsory measures	Emphasise a more flexible, voluntary approach to behaviour change that encourages individuals and businesses to adopt sustainable practices through positive reinforcement, rather than imposing strict mandates and penalties.
	Standardisation of prices in RES	Simplify market entry for new players, enhance transparency, and drive competition, ultimately supporting the widespread adoption and integration of RES.
	Integrate EU Legislation into Education	Ensure that training programs and curricula include content on the EU's Renewable Energy Directive, emissions standards, and sustainable fuel regulations to align education with policy needs.

Category	Recommendation	Brief Description
	Training for Public Authorities	Provide upskilling opportunities for public authorities on sustainable and renewable fuels, ensuring they are informed on emerging technologies and can effectively implement and monitor regulations.
Educational/Academia	Establishment of a dedicated European Academy on Renewables	Create a specialised academy for research, education, and collaboration in renewable energy fields. Foster interdisciplinary learning and research by establishing joint degree programs across European universities in RES.
	Alignment of training programs with industry needs	Ensure that training programs in renewable energy align with industry needs to prepare a skilled workforce. Promote collaboration between academia and industry through industrial programs, theses, internships and hands-on training, laboratory sessions, and industry traineeships in all degree programs
	Including the industry and private sector in educational boards	Ensure that curricula are aligned with current market needs and technological advancements, fostering a closer link between academic training and real-world industry requirements.
	Hands-on training on renewable energy experience with interactive learning and innovative methods	Provide practical, experiential learning opportunities that enhance participants' understanding and skills. By utilising advanced techniques such as simulations, virtual reality, and real-world applications, this approach effectively bridges the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application in the renewable energy sector.
	Reskilling the traditional workforce	Include skills such as technical expertise combined with business skills, or adapting to emerging industry demands. This approach ensures that workers and students are equipped with a diverse skill set that integrates technical knowledge with strategic financial planning, enhancing their ability to contribute to and thrive in rapidly changing fields.

Category	Recommendation	Brief Description
	Enhance Digital and Data Skills	Incorporate statistics, big data, and digital monitoring tools into education, including simulation software and AI-based approaches for sustainable systems.
	Interdisciplinary and Cross-Topic Curricula	Design curricula that integrate renewable energy subtopics (e.g., PV, wind, storage, smart cities) and promote project-based, cross-disciplinary learning.
	Train the Trainers Programmes	Develop a network of educators trained in modern renewable energy systems, pedagogy, and technologies to cascade knowledge across sectors and regions.
Financial	Incentives for individuals and companies adopting RES	Include tax breaks, subsidies, and other financial benefits that reduce the cost of adopting renewable energy technologies, thereby encouraging wider implementation and supporting the growth of a green economy.
	Fund multiple projects in specific fields	Fund several promising projects within a specific field to increase innovation and success rates, even using unused resources from programs like Horizon Europe.
	Grants and subsidies for equipment enhancement in vocational schools	Offer financial incentives to improve resources in vocational training institutions.
	Grants and subsidies for continuous education and certifications on RES	Financial support aims at fostering lifelong learning and professional development in the field. By reducing the cost of further education and certification, these incentives help individuals and organisations stay updated with the latest advancements and best practices, thereby enhancing expertise and ensuring a skilled workforce in the renewable energy sector.

Category	Recommendation	Brief Description
	Incentives for industrial PhDs	Provide tax incentives for companies that support industrial PhD programs to encourage advanced research and innovation.
	Green Business & Finance in Tech Education	Integrate green business models and green finance topics into engineering and technology programs to prepare students for the economic dimensions of the green transition.
	Promote Innovation Hubs	Support the creation of interdisciplinary research centres focused on the renewable energy value chain, encouraging collaboration and innovation with potential funding support mechanisms.
Social	Engagement of society	Encourage the active participation of local communities in renewable energy projects, providing hands-on training and involvement in project development.
	Promote hands-on renewable energy experience via mobility programmes	Facilitate practical experiences such as internships, seminars and field visits to enhance understanding and skills in renewable energy environments, and thus change users' behavioural patterns.
	Raise public awareness of renewable energy derivatives	Conduct public awareness campaigns to inform and educate citizens about the benefits and necessity of adopting renewable energy.
	Address energy poverty	Implement policies to ensure affordable and accessible energy options for all individuals, considering income disparities.
	Engagement of women in RES	Involve women in various roles within the sector. This includes promoting gender diversity, supporting Women's rights NGOs/Organisations, and creating opportunities for women to participate in RES projects and leadership positions. This leverages diverse perspectives and skills,

Category	Recommendation	Brief Description
		enriching the overall innovation and effectiveness of the renewable energy sector.
	Digital hub platform for renewables experts	Establish a digital platform to facilitate communication and knowledge exchange among experts in the field of renewable energy.
	Use of AR/VR for Youth Engagement	Integrate immersive technologies (e.g., AR/VR) to engage younger audiences in sustainable mobility and energy education early on

Common Themes and Areas of Consensus

- **Financial Incentives:** Many recommendations across categories emphasise the importance of subsidies, tax breaks, grants, and financial schemes to incentivise investment in renewable electricity, sustainable mobility, fuels and heat, and support mechanisms to facilitate the transition to renewable energy sources.
- **Education and Training:** There is a strong emphasis on enhancing educational programs, fostering industry-academia collaboration, and promoting skills development in green technologies.
- **Community Engagement:** Recommendations highlight the role of community involvement and awareness in driving the adoption of sustainable practices in the energy, mobility, and heating sectors.
- **Regulatory Support:** Calls for harmonisation of national regulations with EU directives, the standardisation of values and regulations, and the removal of bottlenecks in legislation.
- **Integration and Collaboration:** There is widespread agreement on the need for integrating policies across different sectors (energy, mobility, heat) and fostering collaboration between stakeholders (industry, academia, communities).

Differing Viewpoints

- **Emphasis on Specific Technologies:** Some recommendations focus heavily on specific technologies (e.g. electric vehicles, waste heat recovery) while others advocate for a broader approach that includes various technological solutions.

2.1.3 Emerging Skills Summary

The table below offers an aggregated and categorised version of the most emerging skills derived from the WG meetings

Table 3. SKILLBILL emerging skills

	Electricity	Heat	Fuels	Mobility	Transversal
Urgent Immediate need in the industry		Calculate the economic feasibility of geothermal and heat reuse investments	Design storytelling campaigns around new fuel technologies	Use GIS tools for EV network planning	Management Leadership/Coaching
Future Relevant important in 3–5 years	Design integrated systems combining PV, battery storage, and hydrogen	Design and retrofit district heating systems using renewable sources			Public Speaking Simulate energy/mobility scenarios using software
Underdeveloped requiring long-term development in training and education			Operate small-scale Power-to-X and biomethane production systems		

2.1.4 Job Profiles

The figure below offers an overview of the most important job profiles derived from the WG meetings

Figure 2. SKILLBILL Job Profiles

3. Conclusion

This report presents the summarised outcomes of the four Working Groups (WGs) established under the SKILLBILL Stakeholder Joint Initiative, focusing on Renewable Electricity, Sustainable Mobility, Renewable Fuels, and Renewable Heat.

Altogether, the process brought together diverse expertise to address the advancement of Renewable Energy Systems (RES) in Europe. A total of **177 recommendations** were developed within the scope of working groups' meetings covering sustainable electricity, mobility, fuels, and heating sectors. These are summarised in this report titled "SKILLBILL Working Group Insights" and offer a practical roadmap to support European climate and sustainability objectives.

The recommendations have been categorised into four key areas - **Political/Regulatory, Educational/Academic, Financial, and Social** - with common themes such as financial incentives, education and training, community engagement, regulatory support, integration, and collaboration. They also highlight both areas of divergence across stakeholder perspectives, such as specific technologies under each sector.

The project

SKILLBILL's overall objective is to develop a large and strong foundation for the growth and acceleration of renewable energy's deployment, thanks to engaging with stakeholders of the whole chain, diffusing scientific culture and skilling multi-level workers. The basic idea underling the project is that the knowledge should be diffused at several different levels and qualitatively appropriate both to train the adequate number of workers and to increase RES awareness and to reach a more social and inclusive Europe. The project aims at creating several pathways to induce target groups to get interested or involved in RES besides their initial level of education and their working position. It's important, beside the creation of instruments for the upskilling and reskilling of workers, technician and designers, to have awareness modules for unpecific public in order to fight against lack of information, bad quality material, gender gap and the phenomenon of functional illiteracy: it is widely documented that lifelong suitable learning process is the fundamental driver to support the development, maintenance and update of skills. Thus, SKILLBILL proposes concrete actions to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy at different levels to analyse and involve all the interested parts in open discussion using adequate language; create several different pathways to increase skills after having mapped knowledge gap and without gender prejudice; develop and implement innovative learning method; and evaluate the work performed.

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